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CONCRETING OF LAKE SHORELINES UNDER COMPLEX ANTHROPOGENIC PRESSURE: CONSEQUENCES FOR THE BIODIVERSITY OF MACROPHYTES, FISH, AND WATERBIRDS

Abstract. Shoreline concreting is a widespread anthropogenic pressure in urban lakes, yet its cross-trophic effects remain insufficiently quantified. This study assesses the combined impact of littoral vegetation removal, shoreline hardening, and petroleum contamination on macrophyte, fish, and waterbird communities in a hydrologically connected urban lake system in Kyiv, Ukraine. Field surveys were conducted in 2018–2020 and 2023. In 2019, 25% of the Lake Kyrlyvske shoreline was concreted and 6.5% converted into beach area, accompanied by large-scale vegetation removal; in 2021, petroleum pollution affected approximately 25% of the lake surface. Fish species richness declined from 20 to 10 species, followed by partial recovery to 15 species in 2023, with the appearance of the invasive *Lepomis gibbosus*. Macrophyte richness increased from 9 to 15 species, indicating partial vegetation recovery. Bird communities showed stable species richness but increased abundance of piscivorous species.

These results indicate coordinated cross-trophic responses to shoreline transformation, emphasizing the importance of preserving vegetated littoral zones for maintaining biodiversity in urban lake ecosystems.

Keywords: shoreline concreting, urban lakes, littoral zone, macrophytes, ichthyofauna, waterbirds, cross-trophic interactions, biodiversity, Ukraine, anthropogenic impact

The study area covers approximately 18.4 ha. In 2019, extensive shoreline modification measures were implemented at Lake Kyrlyvske, including the removal of coastal and aquatic vegetation such as reeds, shrubs, and trees. These interventions resulted in the transformation of large sections of the shoreline into a continuous beach zone. In addition, a portion of the Syrets River, which discharges into the lake, was artificially channelized and reinforced with concrete. At present, the total shoreline length of Lake Kyrlyvske is 2.14 km, of which 25.0% (536 m) is occupied by newly constructed concrete embankments, while 6.5% (140 m) has been converted into beach area; the remaining sections have partially recovered to a near-natural state. In autumn 2021, following these modifications, an accidental discharge of petroleum products from the Syrets River occurred, contaminating approximately one quarter of the lake's surface. Changes in the abundance and species composition of aquatic macrophytes, fish, and bird communities, key structural components of freshwater ecosystems, provide a basis for an integrated assessment of ecosystem condition, including differentiation between strictly aquatic and water-associated (wetland-dependent) components.

Macrophytes In 2015, a total of nine species of aquatic macrophytes were recorded. The community was dominated by *Phragmites australis*, *Typha angustifolia*, *Ceratophyllum demersum*, and *Potamogeton crispus*, with additional occurrences of *Butomus umbellatus*, *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Najas marina*, *Lemna minor*, and *Myriophyllum spicatum*. Subsequent surveys conducted in 2023 revealed a marked increase in species richness, with a total of fifteen macrophyte species identified. The dominant taxa shifted towards *Phragmites australis* and *Najas marina*. The assemblage also included *Typha angustifolia*, *Eleocharis palustris*, *Agrostis stolonifera*, *Glyceria maxima*, *Bolboschoenus maritimus*, *Iris pseudacorus*, *Sparganium erectum*, *Scirpus lacustris*, *Alisma plantago-aquatica*, *Potamogeton crispus*, *Potamogeton perfoliatus*, *Ceratophyllum demersum*, and *Lemna minor*.

Ichthyofauna During the study period beginning in 2018, the fish community comprised 20 species belonging to six families: Cyprinidae, Percidae, Syngnathidae, Odontobutidae, Esocidae, and Gobiidae. The assemblage was numerically dominated by *Alburnus alburnus* (25%),

Scardinius erythrophthalmus (19.0%), *Perca fluviatilis* (17.4%), and *Neogobius fluviatilis* (17.4%).

By 2020, following shoreline modification and the petroleum contamination event, species richness declined to ten fish species. Several taxa were no longer recorded in catches, including *Abramis brama*, *Squalius cephalus*, *Idus idus*, *Sander lucioperca*, *Gymnocephalus cernuus*, and *Esox lucius*. A pronounced reduction was observed in phytophilous species, whose reproductive success is closely linked to the availability of submerged and emergent vegetation along the littoral zone. In particular, the abundance of *Scardinius erythrophthalmus* declined fivefold, while *Leucaspis delineatus* decreased fourfold. Additional declines were documented for *Rutilus rutilus* and *Perca fluviatilis*. In contrast, the relative abundance of *Alburnus alburnus* increased by approximately 1.8 times, likely reflecting reduced predation pressure and the loss of more sensitive and predatory species.

In 2023, the fish assemblage comprised 15 species, with *Alburnus alburnus* (34.0%) and *Scardinius erythrophthalmus* (23.2%) representing the most abundant taxa. The recovery of previously recorded species, including common carp *Cyprinus carpio*, *Gymnocephalus cernuus*, and *Esox lucius*, was not confirmed. At the same time, the invasive species *Lepomis gibbosus* was recorded in the lake. A substantial reduction in available spawning substrates, combined with intensified contamination of bottom waters, was associated with a restructuring of dominance patterns within the fish community, affecting both dominant and subdominant species.

Ornithofauna The effects of cumulative anthropogenic pressure were most pronounced in *Ixobrychus minutus*, whose abundance declined from six individuals in 2016–2018 to a single individual in 2018–2019. By 2023, however, its abundance had increased to eight individuals. A comparable trajectory was observed for *Fulica atra*.

The occurrence of piscivorous birds, including representatives of the genus *Larus* and *Podiceps cristatus*, increased two- to fourfold after 2019, whereas *Phalacrocorax carbo* remained relatively stable throughout the study period. Despite substantial alterations to the shoreline structure of Lake Kyrlyivske, no significant decline in overall bird species richness was detected (Table 1).

The observed patterns indicate species-specific responses within the bird assemblage. While the abundance of some species declined and subsequently recovered, others, particularly piscivorous taxa, showed a sustained increase after 2020. These dynamics are likely linked to changes in macrophyte cover and concurrent shifts in fish community structure. Differences in relative fish abundance among sampling periods further reflect ecosystem-level responses to shoreline transformation.

The recovery of phytophilous fish species and associated waterbird populations appears to be related to the expansion of aquatic and riparian vegetation. In particular, the marked increase in the abundance of the great crested grebe (*Podiceps cristatus*) likely reflects improved trophic conditions, associated with increased fish availability in the lake.

Table 1 (continued). Changes in the species composition and abundance of fish (% of total catch) and waterbirds (number of individuals) during 2016–2023.

Fish species	Number, %			Bird species	Number of individuals		
	2018	2020	2023		2018	2019	2023
<i>Squalius cephalus</i>	0.7	–	3.1	<i>Larus ridibundus</i>	12	12	14
<i>Idus idus</i>	4.5	–	–	<i>L. cachinnans</i>	2	3	2
<i>Abramis brama</i>	3.0	–	6.3	<i>L. canus</i>	6	4	–
<i>Leucaspis delineatus</i>	3.8	2.4	3.2	<i>Sterna hirundo</i>	4	6	4
<i>Blicca bjoerkna</i>	1.5	1.2	8.0	<i>Podiceps cristatus</i>	2	2	6
<i>Alburnus alburnus</i>	18.9	55.5	30.1	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	3	3	3

<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	2.2	–	–	<i>Ixobrychus minutus</i>	6	1	8
<i>Scardinius erythrophthalmus</i>	16.6	5.0	20.6	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	8	8	16
<i>Rutilus rutilus</i>	2.2	1.2	6.3	<i>Fulica atra</i>	16	4	20
<i>Carassius auratus</i>	1.5	2.4	1.6	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	6	4	4
<i>Rhodeus amarus</i>	2.2	3.7	3.1	<i>Acrocephalus arundinaceus</i>	4	3	8
<i>Sander lucioperca</i>	0.7	–	1.6	<i>A. scirpaceus</i>	1	–	4
<i>Perca fluviatilis</i>	15.1	19.7	7.9	<i>Remiz pendulinus</i>	–	2	–
<i>Gymnocephalus cernuus</i>	5.3	–	–	Total number of individuals	70	52	89
<i>Syngnathus nigrolineatus</i>	0.7	–	–				
<i>Perccottus glenii</i>	0.7	–	–				
<i>Neogobius fluviatilis</i>	15.1	6.17	1.6				
<i>N. gymnotrachelus</i>	1.51	2.4	1.6				
<i>Proterorhinus semilunaris</i>	1.51	–	1.6				
<i>Lepomis gibbosus</i>	–	–	3.1				
Total number of species	20	10	15				

Conclusions

The removal of natural vegetation cover around Lake Kyrylivske, in combination with the concreting of 25% of its shoreline and the transformation of 6.5% into beach area, led to a marked disturbance of habitats for macrophytes, fish, and birds in 2019. By 2023, partial recovery of biodiversity was observed, reflected in increased macrophyte species richness and higher bird abundance. However, the recovery of fish diversity remained incomplete, and the emergence of an invasive species indicates ongoing structural changes within the ecosystem.